

NOTES

2. R. A. PAWAR and S. M. JAIN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 304; R. A. PAWAR, A. L. KOHAK and V. N. GOGTE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1976, 14, 375; R. A. PAWAR, 9th IOHO, Japan, 1983, Abstracts G-144, 506.
3. R. A. PAWAR, R. D. SHINGTE and V. N. GOGTE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 522; R. A. PAWAR and V. N. GOGTE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, 19, 921.
4. A. R. KATRITZKY and A. P. AMBLER, in "Physical Methods in Heterocyclic Chemistry", ed. A. R. KATRITZKY, Academic, New York, 1968, Vol. II, p. 232.
5. E. S. GOULD, "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry", Holt, Rinehart of Winston, New York, 1959, p. 150.

appearing at δ 6.2–9.1 were supported by D_2O exchange. In case of the amides (**1**, **2**; $R' = n$ -alkyl) signal due to $CH=CR$ proton was observed at δ 8.2–8.4.

1

- 1a**; $R = 2-NO_2$, $R' = H$, n -alkyl ($C_1 - C_6$)
1b; $R = 3-NO_2$, $R' = H$, n -alkyl ($C_1 - C_6$)
1c; $R = 4-NO_2$, $R' = H$, n -alkyl ($C_1 - C_6$)
1d; $R = 2-Cl$, $R' = H$, OH_2 , C_2H_5
1e; $R = 3-Cl$, $R' = H$, OH_2 , C_2H_5
1f, $R = 4-Cl$, $R' = H$, OH_2 , C_2H_5

Synthesis and J.H. Activity of *N*-(Substituted)-yl-3-(sub-1'-phenyl)acrylamides and *N*-(Substituted)-yl-2-alkyl-3(sub-1'-phenyl)-acrylamides

M. S. BHATIA*, ARVINDER KAUR, B. KAUR
and

XAVIER M. CHERIAN**

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University,
Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 11 April 1988, revised 18 September 1988,
accepted 12 October 1988

2

- 2a**, $R = 2-NO_2$, $R' = H$, CH_3 , C_2H_5
2b; $R = 3-NO_2$, $R' = H$, CH_3 , C_2H_5 , $n-C_6H_{11}$
2c; $R = 4-NO_2$, $R' = H$, OH_2
2d; $R = 2-Cl$, $R' = H$, OH_2
2e; $R = 3-Cl$, $R' = H$, OH_2
2f; $R = 4-Cl$, $R' = H$, OH_2

J.H. activity: The compounds (**1** and **2**) were screened* for their J.H. activity against Indian red cotton bug.

Among amides of cinnamic acid and (*o*, *m*, *p*)-nitro-substituted acids with cyclohexylamine, *p*-nitro-substituted compound (**1c**; $R' = H$) showed the highest activity. Activity decreased as nitro group moved from *para* to *ortho* position. Similar trend in activity was observed in case of chloro-substituted amides (*para* > *meta* > *ortho*). As the length of the alkyl chain at C-2 of **1c** was increased, a decrease in activity was noted. Replacement of cyclohexyl system in **1** by pyrazolone system **2** showed increase in activity.

Experimental

M.p./b.p. were uncorrected. Pmr spectra were recorded on a EM/390 (90 MHz) spectrometer. Hplc was carried out on a Simadzu-LCUA instrument. All the compounds showed satisfactory elemental analysis and spectral data.

General procedure for preparation of substituted acrylic acids: To sodium hydride (0.1 mol, 50% emulsion in mineral oil) was taken in dry THF (75 dm³), appropriate Wittig's salt (0.1 mol) was added dropwise with stirring keeping temperature below 20° and the reaction mixture was further stirred for 3 h at room temperature. The contents were then cooled and decomposed with excess water. The organic material was extracted with ether and the

DURING the past two decades, efforts are being made to find an alternative mode of insect control because of their poisonous nature to non-target organisms and resistance by insects. Causing disarrangement of insect growth processes with their own hormones or related compounds, specifically with J.H. analogues, has been the subject of interest¹.

In continuation to our earlier studies² on the synthesis and J.H. activity of multifunctional amides, a number of substituted amides (**1** and **2**) have been synthesised and tested for their J.H. activity on Indian red cotton bug.

Substituted cinnamic acids were prepared through the applications of modified Wittig's reaction³ with appropriate reagents on *o*-, *m*- and *p*-substituted-benzaldehydes followed by hydrolysis with aqueous base.

Reaction of substituted cinnamic acids with an amine in presence of $POCl_3$ /triethylamine in dichloromethane furnished the required amides (**1** and **2**), whose structures were confirmed by pmr and hplc.

Double bond fixed by modified Wittig's reaction was predominantly *E* confirmed by hplc analysis which exhibited two peaks with average retention time of 2.6 (97.2%) and 3.2 (2.8%) corresponding to *E* and *Z* isomers, respectively. It is also attributed to the presence of pmr signals at δ 8.6 and 6.25 ($-CH=CH-$). The presence of NH protons

**Present address: Department of Chemistry, The Ohio State University, U.S.A.

solvent distilled off to get the respective unsaturated ester in good yield.

A mixture of the unsaturated esters (0.1 mol) in methanol (20 dm³) and aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (10% ; 80 dm³) was refluxed for 8 h. After cooling, the unreacted ester was extracted with ether, and the separated aqueous layer was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the residue filtered to obtain the required acids in 60–67% yield.

Preparation of the amides (1, 2): To a well-stirred solution of the respective acid (10 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (50 dm³) at 0° containing triethylamine (5 mmol) and the appropriate amine (10 mmol) was added a solution of phosphorus oxychloride (10 mmol) in dichloromethane (20 dm³). Additional triethylamine (7 mmol) was added to it in one instalment. The contents were stirred for 0.5 h at 0° and continued stirring for further 6 h at room temperature. Progress of the reaction was studied by tlc at regular intervals. The excess reagents were decomposed by pouring it on crushed ice and the organic layer was extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 20 dm³). The organic extract was washed with 10% aqueous sodium carbonate solution (to remove unreacted acid) followed by water, 10% HCl (to separate unreacted amine) and finally with water. After drying over anhydrous calcium chloride, the solvent was evaporated. The residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and chloroform mixture (3 : 2) as eluent to get the amide.

References

1. M. SCHWARZ, P. E. SONNET and N. WAKALYASHI, *Science*, 1970, 191, 3914; V. K. JAROLIN, F. SLAMA and F. SORM, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, 86, 121568; P. PICCARDI, P. MASSARDO and F. BETTARINI, *Pestic. Sci.*, 1980, 2, 423; O. P. VIG, I. R. TRIFAN and S. KUMARI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, 21, 1169; O. P. VIG, I. R. TRIFAN and G. L. KAD, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, 21, 1059.
2. M. S. BHATIA, B. KAUR, M. O. XAVIERKUTTY and G. SINGH, *Int. Pest Cont.*, 1986, 28, 146; M. S. BHATIA, P. RANI, M. O. XAVIERKUTTY and J. LAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, 64, 411.
3. W. D. WADSWORTH and W. S. EMMONS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, 82, 1733.
4. O. P. VIG, A. JATA and S. KUMARI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, 17, 54.

Synthesis and Biological Activity of 1-Aroyl-5-(p-sulphamylphenylazo)-3,4-dimethylpyrano[2,3-c]pyrazol-6(1H)-ones

M. B. HOGALE* and B. N. PAWAR

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004
 Manuscript received 5 July 1988, accepted 2 November 1988

PYRAZOLES are found to possess various biological activities¹. Here, we report the synthesis of the title compounds and evaluate their biological activities. The synthesis involved the condensation

of substituted-arylohydrazines with ethylacetoacetate in dioxane to give 2-ethyl butyrate-2-substituted-arylohydrazones (1). 1 underwent cyclodehydration with *o*-dichlorobenzene to give 3-methyl-(1-substituted-arylo)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (2) in good yields (Scheme 1). The pyrazolones (2) formed were the mixture of keto and enol forms, explained on the basis of nmr spectral (taken in TFA) studies. In most of the cases, a two-proton signal at δ 2.5 and another at δ 5–6 depending upon the structure, were observed. The enol form is stabilised by the keto group at aroyl/aryloxy substituent at N₁-position of pyrazolone. Here, the formation of 3a–q from 2a–q occurs through the intermediacy of 2a–q and it is the enol form which is responsible for further reactions. The compounds have been characterised by the observation of ir band at 1740 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl), and two pmr signals at δ 2.3 (C₃-methyl) and 2.45 (C₄-methyl).

Scheme 1

Biological activity: All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity using cup-plate agar diffusion technique² against gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas pyocyanea* at 25 and 50 μg ml⁻¹ concentrations using tetracycline as a standard.

The compounds were also tested for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* using agar-plate method³ with Dithan M-45 as a standard commercial fungicide at 1000, 100 and 10 ppm concentrations. The data indicate that the presence of sulphamyl moiety plays key role in the fungitoxicity of the compounds.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 instrument using TMS as an internal reference.